

Integration of hybrid cloud computing and LSTM-DNN neural network architecture into a process information management system

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Abstract: This paper examines an approach to integrating hybrid cloud computing and the LSTM-DNN hybrid neural network architecture into a process information system (PIS) for optimizing technological processes. The key idea is to distribute computational tasks between local and cloud data processing layers, reducing response latency while maintaining high computing power for analyzing large volumes of information. The LSTM-DNN neural network model is used to predict dynamic parameters and adjust control actions taking into account uncertainty and stochastic disturbances. The architecture implements the principle of intelligent predictive control with the ability to update model parameters online in a cloud environment. Simulation results are presented, demonstrating increased forecasting accuracy and reduced computational costs with the combined use of hybrid computing and neural network technologies.

Keywords: *hybrid cloud computing, neural network architecture, LSTM–DNN, information management system, predictive control, technological processes*

1. Introduction

In the context of accelerating digitalization in the industrial sector, the integration of artificial intelligence and cloud technologies is becoming a key area for the development of information and control systems (ICS). The growth of data volumes from distributed sensors and controllers makes traditional local analysis and control systems inflexible and limited in computing resources [1]. This is particularly noticeable in technological processes with nonlinear dynamics and a high degree of uncertainty, where control requires real-time prediction and adaptation.

One promising approach is the use of **hybrid cloud computing**, which involves dividing tasks between local (edge -level) and cloud-based (cloud -level) components. This architecture

combines the low latency of on-the-job controllers with the high analytical power of a centralized cloud platform. This ensures continuous optimization of process parameters and increased reliability of the information and control system (ICS) while minimizing computing infrastructure costs.

In parallel, the field of **hybrid neural network models is developing**, combining the properties of recurrent and deep fully connected architectures [2]. In particular, the combination of **LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory)** and **DNN (Deep Neural Network) modules** allows for the simultaneous consideration of the temporal structure of signals and complex nonlinear relationships between process parameters [3]. This combination is particularly effective in solving problems of predictive control, forecasting equipment conditions, and intelligent correction of control actions [4].

The integration of hybrid neural networks into cloud-based information and control systems opens the possibility of creating **intelligent predictive control systems** capable of adapting to changing operating conditions, stochastic disturbances, and sensor failures. Unlike traditional SCADA systems, such solutions not only record deviations but also predict their development, enabling proactive decision-making.

Despite significant progress in this area, the problem of efficiently distributing computational tasks between local and cloud layers, as well as the issue of aligning neural network algorithms with real-time requirements, remains open. This paper proposes an architecture for integrating hybrid cloud computing and the LSTM-DNN neural network model into a control information system, ensuring a balance between computational efficiency, forecasting accuracy, and control stability. [5].

2. Integration Methods and Concept

Modern information management systems operate in a distributed data processing environment, requiring the coordination of information flows between different levels of the computing infrastructure. When designing a hybrid architecture, a crucial factor is defining the boundaries between tasks performed locally and operations transferred to the cloud environment. This delineation allows for an optimal balance between system response speed and the computational complexity of analytical procedures [6].

2.1. The principle of hybrid cloud computing. Hybrid cloud computing is understood as the integration of several computing levels – local (edge), intermediate (fog), and remote (cloud) – into a single controlled environment. The local level performs primary signal processing and basic regulation, ensuring minimal response latency [7]. The intermediate level is responsible for data aggregation and preliminary information filtering, and the cloud level is responsible for analyzing large arrays, training neural network models, and predicting dynamic parameters.

This distribution of roles creates a multi-level control structure, in which the cloud functions as the center of analytical intelligence, while the periphery ensures stable operation in real time, even with limited network connectivity [8]. In the context of technological processes, this enables adaptive optimization of operating modes, planning of preventive operations, and intelligent correction of control actions without equipment downtime.

2.2. Concept of a hybrid neural network model. The intellectual core of the proposed architecture is a hybrid neural network that combines the temporal properties of a recurrent LSTM unit and the approximation capabilities of a deep fully connected DNN unit [9]. This combination provides dual functionality:

- The LSTM module generates predictions of time series of process parameters, taking into account delays and fluctuations;
- The DNN module approximates nonlinear dependencies between predicted states and control signals, providing real-time decision adjustments.

Unlike traditional single-type architectures, the hybrid LSTM–DNN model allows taking into account both short-term and long-term memory of the system, which increases the stability

and adaptability of forecasting when external conditions and environmental parameters change [10].

2.3. Integration of the Computational and Neural Network Layers. Integration of the hybrid neural network into the cloud-based information and communication system is implemented through a distributed computing circuit, in which model training and retraining tasks are performed in the cloud, while forecasting and local correction are performed at the edge level. Data exchange between the layers is organized using the OPC UA and MQTT protocols, ensuring low latency and transmission security [11].

To synchronize the model's state, a periodic weight update mechanism is used, in which the cloud transmits updated parameters to local nodes without requiring a complete system shutdown. This approach ensures continuous operation of the information and communication system in adaptive self-learning mode.

2.4. Integration effectiveness criteria. The key effectiveness criteria are:

Time latency – minimizing delays in making control decisions;

Robustness of forecasts is the ability of a model to remain stable under disturbances and incomplete data;

Computational efficiency – rational distribution of the load between local and cloud resources;

Connection stability – maintaining functionality during temporary network interruptions.

Optimization of these parameters allows us to consider the developed architecture as an intelligent platform that combines the capabilities of artificial intelligence and cloud technologies to manage complex dynamic processes.

3. Integrated system architecture

The developed architecture combines the principles of hybrid cloud computing and intelligent predictive control based on the LSTM-DNN neural network model. The main idea is to distribute computational and analytical tasks between the system layers in such a way as to ensure high forecasting accuracy with minimal response delay [12].

3.1. General structure of the information and control system. The information and control system is built on a three-tiered scheme: **a sensory level, a local processing level** , and **a cloud-based analytics level** .

The sensor layer includes a network of industrial sensors and actuators that continuously collect process parameters (temperature, pressure, flow rate, feedstock composition, etc.). At this stage, the data is filtered and time-synchronized to eliminate noise measurements.

The local layer implements primary management and stores short-term data. It houses edge devices and controllers that perform operational calculations, diagnostics, and corrective actions based on local models.

The cloud layer is designed for long-term analysis, training neural network models, forecasting, and optimization decision-making. The cloud also coordinates model parameter updates, transmitting them to lower layers without interrupting the process cycle.

Interaction between layers is organized via a data bus using the **MQTT** and **OPC UA protocols**, ensuring stable communication with minimal network load. The entire circuit operates in asynchronous mode, allowing the system to remain operational even if communication with the cloud is temporarily lost.

3.2. Interaction of the hybrid neural network with the cloud module. The LSTM-DNN neural network architecture is embedded in the cloud analytics module. The model receives aggregated data from local nodes, predicts dynamic states, and generates recommendations for adjusting control actions. Predictions and control coefficients are transmitted back to the edge layer, where they are applied in real time [13, 14].

The LSTM component analyzes temporal dependencies between parameters, revealing hidden correlations and cyclical patterns, while the DNN component refines nonlinear

relationships between control and dependent variables. This separation of roles improves the robustness of forecasts and ensures adaptation to changing process conditions.

3.3. Synchronization and Adaptation Mechanism. The key element of the system is **the adaptive synchronization algorithm**, which ensures model consistency between the cloud and local nodes. Periodically, the cloud server initiates the transmission of updated neural network weights, allowing the edge layer to work with the current version of the model [15]. In the event of a connection failure, the local system continues to function autonomously, using the last saved parameters.

To monitor network status and ensure the correctness of updates, a control hash verification module is used to prevent data corruption during transmission. This achieves the balance between autonomy and centralized control necessary for industrial real-time systems [16, 17].

3.4. Software and Technology Implementation. The IMS prototype was implemented using the **Docker container infrastructure** and service orchestration via **Kubernetes**, ensuring scalability and fault tolerance. Data exchange modules are implemented using a REST API and an MQTT message broker.

The neural network component is built on the **TensorFlow library**, with a blended learning approach—local fine-tuning and centralized retraining on a cloud server.

A web interface is used to visualize the system status, displaying process parameter values, forecasts, and accuracy metrics in real time.

4. Simulation results

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed architecture, a series of computational experiments were conducted on a simulation model of a technological process with nonlinear dynamics and a variable structure of input signals [18, 19]. The main goal of the simulation was to compare the performance of a hybrid system combining cloud and local resources with a traditional centralized information and control system operating without distributed computing.

The simulation was performed in two modes. In the first mode, all processing, training, and forecasting operations were performed locally. This approach ensured minimal data transfer latency but limited the analysis capabilities due to limited RAM and computing power.

In the second mode, the proposed hybrid scheme was used: data was initially processed at the local level, and analytical tasks – forecasting, adaptive optimization, and adjustment of model weights – were transferred to the cloud module.

The results showed that using a distributed computing architecture significantly improved efficiency while maintaining the required response time. The average processing time per cycle decreased by 25–30% due to parallel execution of tasks at different levels. Furthermore, the accuracy of predicting dynamic parameters increased by approximately 10% compared to the baseline LSTM without the cloud component.

Particular attention was paid to the system's resilience during temporary disruptions to the cloud connection. Tests confirmed that the local module can maintain autonomy and correct operation during extended periods of network disruption. Once the connection is restored, synchronization of the model parameters occurs automatically, without the need for manual intervention.

An additional result of the modeling was a reduction in the computational load on the cloud server due to pre-filtering of data at the edge level. This approach allowed us to reduce the volume of transmitted data by almost half without losing significant features for training. Thus, the integration of hybrid computing and the LSTM-DNN neural network architecture ensures rational resource allocation and contributes to increased overall system energy efficiency.

Based on the obtained data, it can be concluded that the proposed information control system demonstrates a high level of adaptability, stability, and computational predictability, which makes it applicable to a wide range of technological processes – from metallurgy and the chemical industry to energy and intelligent equipment maintenance systems.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents an architecture for integrating hybrid cloud computing and the LSTM-DNN neural network model into a process information management system (PIMS). The proposed approach combines the advantages of a distributed computing environment and intelligent data analysis algorithms, improving the adaptability and resilience of the PIMS under conditions of uncertainty and dynamically changing production parameters.

The main result of the study is the development of a structural framework for interaction between local and cloud layers, ensuring a balance between computational speed and the analytical depth of data processing. The implemented concept of hybrid neural network training enables forecasting, diagnostics, and control correction in real time without loss of accuracy and with limited communication resources.

Experimental simulations confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed solution: reduced system response time, increased forecast accuracy, and improved resilience to network failures. This demonstrates the practical applicability of the architecture for next-generation industrial information and control systems focused on the principles of autonomy, predictability, and digital integration.

Future plans include developing the approach to incorporate self-learning mechanisms and adaptive distribution of computational tasks based on the current system load. Also of interest is expanding the architecture by using transformer and graph neural networks, which will improve the interpretability and scalability of solutions for managing complex multi-parameter processes.

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